

Predicting In Metabolism (RMR)At Rest From Thebody Mass Index Of Advanced In Basketball Players

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 20, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: February 18, 2021</p> <p>Keywords : Basketball, Metabolism, Body Mass Index (BMI)</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4549058</p>	<p><i>That the prediction of the quantities of calories necessary for basketball players necessary to maintain activity, that athletes increase their metabolism rate through physical performance to ten times during one hour or more, and that basketball is one of the games in which the performance is characterized by "repeated ups, attacks and returns to Defense, because it depends on glycolysis without the availability of oxygen (anaerobic). (2,475) and the arithmetic mean of length (189,533) and a deviation (8,288), and the arithmetic mean of body mass reached (24,317) and the deviation for it was (2,455). The first measurement was made 48 hours before the start of the league and the second measurement was during the rest period between the first and second round and the third measurement after the end The periodicity through a predictive equation (the indirect method for calculating the metabolism index (metabolism). As for the most important conclusions that were reached, the results showed that there were no significant differences in the BMI, meaning that the effort Physical activity during the cyclic period led to a stabilization in body mass, and the results showed an increase in the metabolic index with the length of the cyclic period through an increase in physical exertion.</i></p>

Introduction

Health is considered one of the basic arbiters for the success of the individual in the work that he must perform and that he is entrusted with, whether in his public or sporting life, and in order for this to be done, the physical, psychological and social safety and integration between them must be in order for the individual to enjoy good health, from here he knows (Ibrahim Salama 1997) Health, citing the World Health Organization, as "the state of safety and physical adequacy as psychological and social, and not merely the individual being free from illness or disability, and (Ahmed Taha Salem 2020) indicated that" basketball is one of the games in which performance is distinguished. To "by repetitively ascending, attacking and returning to defense, it depends on glycolysis without the availability of (anaerobic) oxygen, which is known as the lactic acid system. As for the non-oxygenic system that depends on aerobic glycolysis, as the amount of calories resulting from glycolysis per liter of oxygen is equivalent to (5.1) (Kilo calories) a player needs to maintain his muscular activity. "The comfort and facilities created by the modern era of the Renaissance are considered to have negatively affected the integration in the aspects of his physical, psychological, social and mental personality, through robbing The human being for his activity and vitality, despite the fact that it saved him time, effort and money, after the machine had resolved to spend his work after he was relying on himself, until the incidence of diseases such as diabetes, blood pressure, and heart attacks increased, and all of these diseases are related to obesity (Obesity) (Williams (2015)) points out by saying, "That 15-20% of obese people are more likely to die compared to lean people in America annually. As (2016 Zdenko, Reguli& others) pointed out, "The player who possesses the elements of physical formation has physical, skill, and technical capabilities and has the opportunity to win and progress with positive results, and (body weight with height) is an important factor in determining BMI. (BMI) and the volume of both body fat mass. The value of body composition is used in the development of specific physical performance, which helps in designing modular training programs.

With regard to the special studies in metabolism: One of the most important findings of the study is the study (AbdelkaderQaddoumi 2007) that the level of the body mass index (BMI) of the players participating in the Arab Championship for the twentieth Arab clubs and the champion in flying ball was very good. The average reached 23.20 kg / m² and the RMR level, where the current average reached 2076.60 kcal / day and was calculated using predictive equations. As for the study (H. Thorpe, K. Schofield 2018) on female and male basketball players, double x-rays were used. Energy absorption measurement (DXA) to determine the percentage of fat, and predictive equations for calculating the metabolic rate of athletes and predictive equations for non-athletes, taking height and weight to extract the mass, for players of various sports in New Zealand, and the results were varied in the results between the metabolism of athletes at rest and non-athletes Using a special

equation for athletes and non-athletes, and in the study of MICHAEL VOGT, et.al 2003), for highly trained people of various actors and calculating metabolism through a program Especially in the electronic calculator, after taking the height and weight of the players in calculating the mass, it was found after (6) of them were subjected to a 51% high-fat system with training three times a week and (6) players for a low-fat regimen at a rate of 21% and with the same intensity for the two samples for 5 weeks severely 75 - 80% supported this study by the Swiss National Science Foundation, the results were, that the rate of metabolism and the content of the body of fats did not change, this difference was not statistically significant and the percentage of energy from high-concentration fats reached 0.7% of the total energy and energy of fats Low concentration 0.6% when performing 60-90 minutes effort, as in (2019 et.al (Taylor & Francis), (18 players) were monitored for the length of the stoppage of the general rugby league for a period of (14) weeks and the changes in body mass were known. And the rate of change in metabolism by equations and by means of (dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry). This study contradicts the common perception that an increase in skeletal muscle mass will lead to a significant increase in the metabolism rate and daily energy needs, the traditional prediction equations in general less than Athlete's RMR.

The aim of the research:-

- Predicting the quantities of calories needed for basketball players necessary to maintain activity, that athletes increase their metabolism rate through physical performance to ten times during one hour or more
- Knowledge of the metabolic index, the basis of growth processes, the organization of bodily processes, tissue regeneration, and the generation of energy needed for metabolism.

Method and tools

The researcher used the descriptive approach with one group in a consecutive way using repeated tests. The research community, represented by the Premier League basketball teams for the applicants and for the season (2017-2018), was chosen from the clubs of the participants in the Premier League competitions, which amounted to (80) players, which is (55.6%)) From the population of the original sample, and the sample specifications are as shown in Table (1).

Table (1) Statistical description of the search sample in the variables (length, chronological age, mass)

skensses	error std.v	Mode	Mean	measuring unit	variables
0.948	14.106	84.000	87.800	Kg	Weight
0.316	8.228	187.000	189.533	Cm	Length
-0.150	2.475	23.000	22.867	Years	Age
0.509	2.455	24.020	24.317	M ² / Kg	BMI

As for the procedures and measurements, they included:

The first measurement: - The main experiment was conducted in the indoor police club hall for sports at the beginning of December 2017, at (4 pm) before the start of the league in (48 hours), as the height and weight of the players were taken to extract the body mass ((BMI BMI) = (weight / square length) units (kg / m²) (and the formula (De Lorenzo, A.et.al (1999)) is applied to extract the metabolic rate

$$\text{RMR} = (- 857) + (9.0 \times \text{BMI}) + (11.7 \times \text{H})$$

The second measurement: - The second measurement was made after the end of the first phase in February of 2018 at 4 pm in the closed police club hall for the games, and the same procedures were done for the first major experiment

1. **The third measurement:** - The third test was conducted after the end of the tournament at the beginning of (April) of 2018 at (4 pm) in the closed police club hall for games, and the same procedures were done for the first and second experience.

Results

Table (2) The significance test shows the differences between the results of repeated measurements of body mass and metabolism

Sigdegree	McCleoy's test, in terms of a value (Huynh-Feldt)	standard deviation	mean	unit of measure	mass
0.000	0.122	3.72	23.53	kg / m ²	Test 1

		2.56	24.59	kg / m2	Test 2
		2.46	24.48	kg / m2	Test 3
Metabolism					
0.002	0.864	34.155	231.982	calories / day	Test 1
		20.344	238.446	calories / day	Test 2
		21.924	247.150	calories / day	Test 3

.Significant at (Sig) <(0.05

Table (3)Shows the significance of the differences in BMI and metabolism between the three tests

Sig.	F	mean square	df	sum of squares	(BMI)	
0.078	3.53	9.49	1.07	10.11	factor1	Huynh-Feldt
		2.69	14.91	40.04	Error (factor1)	
Metabolism						
0.002	7.167	4358.998	1.728	7531.351	factor1	uynh-Feldt
		608.209	110.577	67254.128	Error (factor1)	

Significant at (Sig) <(0.05).

Table (4)It shows the difference of the arithmetic mean for the three tests in terms of L.S.D

Sig in favor of ..	Sig	standard error	Difference of mean	Metabolism	
non	0.161	4.597	- 6.464	Test 2	Test 1
Test 3	0.001	4.597	- 15.167	Test 3	
non	0.06	4.597	- 8.703	Test 3	Test 2

Discussion

Through Table (2), it is shown that there is a slight increase in the arithmetic mean in the body mass and the metabolic rate (energy exchange rate) calories / day, between the first and second measurement that the prediction of the metabolic rate indicates that there are no significant differences between the two measurements, The rate of metabolism (metabolism) is a quantitative measure to know the energy spent and through the index (BMI) so that the athlete does not reach the stage of obesity and through it we reach the amount of energy consumed that should not be higher than the energy spent, and through it the trainer can change the training programs in light of that The data thus preserving the athlete's health, and the amount of energy spent was high during the effort, as (2000 Katch FI, McArdle WD) indicated that "there is no doubt that the relative fat percentage (fat mass) (BF) decreases in the bodies of athletes to a large extent. Because of the intense and continuous training programs that lead to the loss of many calories as a result of burning more energy to sustain performance, which can be confirmed by extracting body mass and the rate of calories spent.

As for the second measurement at the end of the stage, which was made at the end of the first stage and the beginning of the second stage until the end of the league, and through Table (2), it indicated an increase in the rate of metabolism from what it is from the beginning of the first stage to its end with a very small increase in the body mass index (BMI). Table (4) we find that the differences were random, and the researcher believes that the reason is that the energy system in basketball prevailing is the anaerobic system, which constitutes 90%, which is a maximum anaerobic capacity, the performance time is 30 seconds, with the substitutions being open throughout the time of the match and the time of one revenue 10 Minutes and with the interval of 2 minutes, and this is why the results appeared in this way, and as (Abdel Nasser Al-Qaddumi 2003) pointed out that "well-trained athletes do not have the ability to increase the size of fat cells and thus exposure to obesity, as in general there is a convergence between calories Heat intake and consumption,

But with the continuation of the periodicity and through Table (2), we find that there is a large difference in the rate of metabolism with no significant differences in the body mass index (BMI) and Table (4) indicates the emergence of significant differences in the rate of metabolism, as the period of continuation in performance Physical during the continuous league matches was sufficient to increase the metabolic rate, so the results were

significant in favor of the first test, and by comparing the metabolism at the beginning of the league with the metabolism index at the end of the league, knowing the calories through which it is possible to determine the amount of energy needed for the athlete, The American College of Sports Medicine (MCSM) and the American Heart Association (AHA) on physical activity indicated that to promote and maintain body mass and metabolism, athletes should maintain their weight and muscle mass during competition and training periods, as their bodies are less able to accumulate Fatty masses because their physical exercise of (60-90) minutes five days a week in addition to the competition periods increases the rate of metabolism and the dispensing of calories per day and ensures that the mass is not increased Lipid for the athlete. "

Conclusions

- The results showed that there were no significant differences in body mass index, meaning that physical exertion during the period of the league led to a stability in body mass.
- The results also showed an increase in the metabolism index with the length of the league period through an increase in the physical effort exerted by the players.

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